

A CREEP MODEL FOR THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID BI-STABLE LAMINATE

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1. INTRODUCTION

Deformable structure is concerned by space because of completing different task at the same size and quality, and parts of deformable structure have been applied to the spacecraft. Conventional deformable structures generally apply sophisticated mechanical or hydraulic system work together to drive the parts for the whole deformation. However, these systems occupy so large space and their larger quality that certain limitation in application, so it is important to investigate the deformable structures which are lightweight, small volume and adaptive. At present, many researchers use bi-stable laminate to prepare the deformable structures for solving the above problem. At present, the research of bi-stable laminate are mainly configuration forecast, curvature, snap-through critical load and the energy collection. But the fatigue of bi-stable laminate is an important issue in the process of jumping over and over again, and the fatigue research of bi-stable laminate are very scarce. This work researchs the fatigue behavior of bistable laminate, gives the critical load changes with the number of cycles and presents a creep model to explain the attenuation range of the critical load.

2. HYBRID BI-STABLE LAMINATE

3. EXPERIMENT

The device of fatigue test

Creep experiment

- Hybrid bi-stable laminate is fabricated by usual autoclave techniques.
- The fatigue experiments are set up by a simple device that is designed for bi-stable fatigue test in motor driver and crank slider, loading frequency 1Hz.
- The plates are always placed in configuration B in creep experiments and the change of critical load is recorded with time.

4. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

- The finite element software ABAQUS is employed to perform the non-linear analysis.
- The cool-down process is from the curing temperature to the room temperature.
- The snap-through is simulated by applying loads after the cool-down simulation. Center remains full constraints and the displacement load is applied in four corners. Then, the displacement load is offloaded in the following analysis.

5. Results and Discussion

- The critical load of bi-stable laminate gradually decreases with the increase of cycle index, and the decline of the critical load is mainly concentrated in the initial time.
- The finite element values and experimental values are close, and the trend and velocity of two curves decline are essentially the same.
- The drop speed of critical load at fatigue test significantly is faster than creep test.

6. CONCLUSIONS

- The fatigue experiment shows the critical load of bi-stable laminate gradually decreases with increasing of cycle index, and critical load decline mainly concentrates in the initial time. The critical load keeps in a fixed value after 10000 times.
- A creep model is present to explain the critical load attenuation. The attenuation speed of critical load at fatigue test significantly is faster than creep test.
- The attenuation amplitude is very close by contrast the two test. The critical load change in fatigue test and creep test. The critical load drop from 2.610N to 1.575N at creep test, and decays 1.035N. The critical load drops from 2.608N to 1.566N at fatigue test, and decays 1.042N.